

IN-SITU SEM STUDY OF MICROCRACKING BEHAVIOR IN CRACK TIP DAMAGE ZONE OF POLYMER MATRIX COMPOSITE *

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ABSTRACT

The microcracking behavior of the material in a crack tip damage zone of polymer matrix composite was continually observed for many hours inside SEM. The processes of the matrix microcracking and their influence on properties of material were discussed. Several sets of valuable SEM photographs are presented which convincingly show the effect of the duration of loading on the microcracking activities in the damage zone. A damage parameter D_{mc} was used to describe the microcracking and its influence on the material properties.

INTRODUCTION

The fiber reinforced polymer matrix composites have been gaining more and more applications as structure materials. One concern with such materials is the delamination which is one of most frequently encountered damage modes in composite structures. The initiation and propagation of delamination through the interfacial debonding tends to significantly reduce the effective stiffness, degrade the strength of materials, and even cause a total failure of structure. Therefore, Substantial efforts have been made to obtain better understanding of the micromechanisms of the delamination damage through experimental investigation and theoretical modelling [1-6].

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Studies showed that the matrix cracking had played a significant role in the initiation and growth of delamination. There exists a strong interaction between matrix cracking and delamination in composites. It seems that matrix cracking can immediately initiate the delamination and significantly affect the delamination propagation [4]. Therefore, it is essential to have a closer look at the matrix cracking activities in the microscale.

Accordingly, the objective of this investigation was to conduct a in-situ scanning electron microscope (SEM) study on matrix microcracking behavior in a crack tip damage zone of resin matrix composite under shear loading in order to obtain better understanding of the micromechanisms of delamination.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

MATERIAL

The material chosen for this investigation was the fiber reinforced epoxy AS4/3502 manufactured by Hercules Corporation. The epoxy 3502 is a highly crosslinked resin. Therefore, the composite AS4/3502 has a high T_g (213°C), and relatively brittle.

SPECIMEN PREPARATION

Miniature end notched flexure (ENF) specimens approximately 30 mm long, 5 mm wide and 1 mm thick were cut from a unidirectional laminate. The specimen surface to be observed by the SEM was ground with sand paper and polished with alumina powder to 0.3 micron finish on an automatic polisher, cleaned, dried, and finally sputter coated with approximately 100 angstrom of a gold-palladium alloy.

SHEAR LOADING THE SPECIMEN INSIDE SEM

Shear loading was performed inside a SEM by using a tensile stage equipped with a load measuring system. Any change in micromechanical behavior of the material in the crack tip damage zone can be monitored.

The specimen was incrementally loaded until a certain load reached. At this point, the load was continually increased to the maximum level or the duration of loading was extended under the load level less than the maximum level. The pictures corresponding to the given load and the duration of loading were taken and analysed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

While the development of damage in fiber reinforced resin matrix composite materials involves multiple failure modes such as matrix microcracking, fiber breakage, delamination, etc. The most dominant modes observed here were matrix microcracking and fiber-matrix debonding.

INITIATION OF MATRIX MICROCRACKING

It has been noted that when the applied shear load increased to certain level, the

Fig. 1 Scanning electron micrograph showing a crack tip damage zone with microcracking activities developing

configuration of the precrack tip began to be blunted. Simultaneously, a long slender crack tip damage zone formed ahead of the crack tip, with some micro-

Fig. 2 Scanning electron micrograph showing the white region in the crack tip damage zone in detail

racks being developed in it, as seen in Fig. 1. Fig. 2 shows a white region of Fig. 1

in high magnification. As can be seen, corrugated bamboo lines developed along a direction approximately 45° relative to the fiber which is responding to the shear stress applied, and microcracks initiated on the bamboo lines in the direction perpendicular to the bamboo line, which results from a normal stress applied locally. Though a global mode II condition has been applied, locally a mode I loading condition is present [5]. Therefore, the material locating in bamboo lines sustains virtually a tensile stress which causes the microcrack initiation.

MICROCRACK GROWTH WITH RAISING LOAD

As the applied load was increased, the microcracks initiated previously began to grow which includes the microcrack stretching, rotating and coalescing, as

Fig. 3 Scanning electron micrograph showing the microcrack growing

shown in Fig. 3. The microcracking activities continued until the maximum load reached and the precrack tip advanced, which tends to initiate a delamination immediately.

MICROCRACKING DURING DURATION OF LOADING

Fig. 4 really shows the effect of the duration of loading on the microcracking behavior in the crack tip damage zone. When the applied load approached a certain level which was close to but less than the maximum load. We stopped increasing the load and were closely looking at the damage zone for hours to see what would actually happen there as the duration of loading extended. It was found that for the microcracking activities there exists 3 stages for the given condition. ① pregnancy stage: at the beginning of holding the load there was not microcrack initiation occurred; ② active microcracking stage: after 30 minutes of holding the load, the microcrack initiating suddenly occurred in several locations, as shown in Fig. 4. (a). Simultaneously, the microcracks locating near the main crack tip and initiated first began to stretch, grow and coalesce, the main crack tip advanced forward, and the crack zone and the damage zone expanded; ③ stable or dynamic equilibrium stage: during this period of time, as seen in Fig. 4 (b) and (c), the microcracking activities were still going on, but the speed is much slower

Fig. 4 Scanning electron micrographs showing the effect of duration of loading on the microcracking behavior in a crack tip damage zone. The durations of loading are respectively: (a) . 30 minutes, (b) . 60 minutes, (c) . 90 minutes, and (d) 660 minutes.

than that in stage two. The total number of accumulated microcrack approached a stable value. The microcracking in the system appears to be in a state of dynamic equilibrium. It seems that there existed two contrary processes in this system. On the one hand, the growing and coalescing of microcracks resulted in the reduction of the total number of the accumulated microcrack in the damage zone. On the other hand, the initiation of new microcrack increased the total number.

It seems that there is a equivalency between extending the duration of loading and continuing to increase the applied load. The effect of them on the microcracking activities appears to be the same.

Based on the discussion above, in the early phase, no microcrack coalescence occurred. So the microcracking behavior of the system in this stage may be described by using the following equation [7]

$$\frac{\partial n}{\partial t} + \sum_{i=1}^i \frac{\partial(nP_i)}{\partial p_i} = n_N \quad (1)$$

Where n is the number density of microcrack, t is the duration of loading, P_i and p_i are variables related to the size of microcrack, and n_N is the nucleation rate of the n .

When the system is in a state of dynamic equilibrium, within certain period of time, the number of microcrack newly initiated approximately equals to the number of microcrack disappeared due to the coalescing. The evolution of microcracking probably follows the following equation:

$$\frac{\partial n}{\partial t} + \sum_{i=1}^i \frac{\partial(nP_i)}{\partial p_i} = n_N - n_A \doteq 0 \quad (2)$$

where n_A is the disappearing rate of microcrack number density.

INFLUENCE OF MICROCRACKING ON PROPERTIES OF MATERIAL

Fig. 5 shows the relationship between load and displacement of the specimen mode II loaded inside a SEM. As can be seen, in the first stage of loading (<7 lbs), in-situ observation found no noticeable microcracking activities going on in the crack tip field. A linear relation between the load and deformation was established. When the applied load level increased to 8 lbs, it was observed that lot of microactivities were happening in the crack tip area: a damage zone was forming and the microcracks were developing in the zone. The change in the curve corresponding to these microactivities is the change in direction of the curve. The linear relation was no longer held.

Due to the microcracking nucleation, and consequent growth and coalescence which damaged the material by reducing net area, many parameters such as

Fig. 5 applied load *vs* displacement

elastic modulus, stiffness, strength which represent the properties of material were degraded. The influence of damage caused by the matrix micracking on the stress in this investigation can be described by using the damage variable D in the continuum damage mechanics [8]. Micracking reduced the area carrying load, and the amount of load carried previously by the area occupied by microcracks now had to be redistributed to the area not occupied by microcracks. Therefore, the nominal stress has to be replaced by the real stress [9], which is related to the damage variable D_{mc} by the following equation:

$$\tau = \frac{\tau_0}{1 - D_{mc}} \quad (3)$$

Where the τ is a real shear stress, and the τ_0 is the nominal stress. The D_{mc} depends on the microcrack density of a plane and represents the degree of damage.

Because the microcracks considered here are generally regarded as being all in one plane, the D_{mc} represents the reduction of the effective area carrying load. Accordingly,

$$D_{mc} = \int ncd\tau = N(t \cdot \tau) \cdot \bar{c}(t, \tau) \quad (4)$$

Where the N is the total number of the microcracks in the system, the c the size of microcrack, and the \bar{c} is the average of the c . The equation (4) clearly indicates that the damage caused by the microcracking depends upon the stress applied and the duration of loading.

SUMMARY

The microcracking behavior in a crack tip damage zone of polymer matrix composite was investigated. Inside a SEM, miniature ENF specimens were continually mode II loaded for many hours. The microcracking activities in the zone were closely observed and analysed during loading and the duration of loading. Results convincingly show that the duration of loading has significant influence on the microcracking. It seems that there exists an equivalence between the extending the duration of loading and increasing the load. It was also indicated that the degradation of material properties results from the reduction of net area carrying load caused by the microcracking, which can be described by a damage variable D_{mc} of the continuum damage mechanics.

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